

relative efficiency of Zn sources and application methods for control of Zn deficiency in wetland rice PR106. The experiment was conducted for 1 yr in a greenhouse with ^{65}Zn and repeated for 2 yr in the field to test the validity of the greenhouse study. Soil characteristics are in Table 1.

Treatments were control (no Zn); 50 ppm Zn as $^{65}\text{ZnSO}_4$ at nursery sowing; dipping nursery seedlings in 2% ^{65}ZnO suspension before transplanting; and 4.5 ppm Zn as $^{65}\text{ZnSO}_4$ at transplanting. Recommended fertilizer doses were applied.

In the greenhouse, Zn content of treated plants was higher than in the control. Early in crop growth, nursery plants enriched with Zn at sowing or as a root dip had relatively higher Zn content than plants receiving Zn at transplanting (Table 2).

Percent Zn in plants was calculated using radioactive zinc (^{65}Zn):

$$\% \text{ Zn from the upland source} = \frac{\text{specific activity of the sample} \times 100}{\text{specific activity of the added source}}$$

Applied Zn contributed 69, 45, and 52% of the total Zn removed by 64-d-old

plants in nursery dip, nursery bed application, and crop application treatments.

Rice grain yield in the field experiments confirmed the greenhouse results. Zn-treated plots yielded 0.6–0.8 t/ha more than the control, but there were no significant differences among Zn treatments (see figure). In the seedling dip treatment, 1 kg ZnO was enough to treat a nursery large enough to transplant 1 ha. Treatment efficiency was similar, but the seedling root dip was most cost efficient, followed by nursery bed application. □

Rice-based cropping systems

Rice - wheat rotation for higher production

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Rice - wheat rotations produced consistently high yields in 909 demonstra-

tions conducted at 17 sites in farmer fields from 1966 to 1982. Sites were in different agroclimatic zones in Uttar Pradesh.

Rice varieties planted were TN1, IR8, and Jaya. Wheat varieties were Sonora 64, Kalyan sona, and Sonalika.

Mean annual yield was 10.6 t/ha (6.0 t rice and 4.6 t wheat). Rice yield ranged from 5.1 to 6.6 t/ha. In a long-range

demonstration in a farmer field, the mean rotation yield was 10.4 t/ha (6.0 t rice and 4.4 t wheat). The highest rice yield was 7.5 t/ha in 1981–82.

Average production cost was \$331.60 and net profit was \$463.20/ha for the rotation. □

Announcements

Conklin awarded Fyssen Foundation prize

Harold C. Conklin, honorary visiting associate scientist at IRRI, was awarded the annual Fyssen Foundation prize for 1983.

The Fyssen Foundation of France, established in 1979, each year recognizes outstanding scientists for their work in such fields as anthropology, ethology, neurology, psychology, paleontology, and archeology. Among those who have received past awards are anthropologist Andre Leroi-Gourhan, ethologist William Thorpe, and neurologist Vernon Mountcastle.

Conklin is an American anthropologist and major innovator in ethnoscience, and

a long-time IRRI cooperator. He is known for his work with the Hanunoo and Ifugao cultures in the Philippines and his *Atlas of Ifugao*.

During his acceptance speech, Conklin emphasized the importance of close work with informants and paid special tribute to them as “indispensable coinvestigators and interpreters of other cultural works . . . It is through their knowledge of the social and natural environment that we come to a better understanding of cultural patterns and their evolution.” □

Ponnamperuma onored

F. N. Ponnamperuma, IRRI principal soil chemist, has been awarded the Doctor

of Science degree by the University of London. Ponnamperuma has worked with IRRI since 1961 and is noted for his work on the chemistry of submerged soils and the nutrition of the rice plant. □

Swaminathan is awarded the R. B. Bennett Commonwealth Prize

M. S. Swaminathan, IRRI director general, has been awarded the 1984 R. B. Bennett Commonwealth Prize by the British Royal Society for the Encouragement of Arts, Manufactures, and Commerce.

Swaminathan is cited for his contributions to agriculture through his work with IRRI, the Government of India, and the Food and Agriculture Organization.